

MODELING EMBEDMENT IN BAMBOO CULMS AND IN FULL-CULM BAMBOO BOLTED CONNECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes a rational methodology for the numerical simulation of embedment phenomena on bamboo. The study adopts the foundation modeling approach, and proposes a rational procedure for the determination of foundation zone size and material properties. Foundation zone material properties are nominal embedment properties, determined via the dowel bearing test. Foundation zone depth occurs rationally from analytical equations that describe the stress field of the culm in the bolt vicinity. Comparison between experimental and numerical model results verify the applicability of the proposed approach for the prediction of experimental strength and stiffness of dowel-bearing tests and bamboo bolted connections.

KEYWORDS

Bamboo; foundation zone; dowel-bearing test; bolted connections

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo has been increasingly popular as a structural material in recent decades, because of its cost-efficiency, high strength-to-weight ratio (Janssen, 1981), and sustainability (Wu et al., 2015). Yet, the round shape of bamboo culms presents difficulties in fabricating reliable connections for full-culm bamboo structural members. A common solution is bolted connections (e.g., Paraskeva et al., 2017, Wang and Yang, 2020), because of their versatility and simplicity. However, bolted connections in cellulosic natural composites (such as bamboo and wood) exhibit intricate failure modes, e.g., splitting and bolt embedment (Hong, 2007, Karagiannis et al., 2016, Paraskeva et al., 2019, Wang and Yang, 2020, Li and Zhou, 2020, Pradhan et al., 2020). Modeling these failure modes is paramount for the prediction of bolted connection behavior, yet it is not an easy task.

Bolt embedment in particular governs connection stiffness, but it complicates connection numerical simulations, as it is the result of local failure (e.g., Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). Bamboo is a natural composite of cellulose fibers encased in a lignin matrix (e.g., Dixon & Gibson, 2014, Wegst et al., 2015, Zhang et al., 2020), but, under local loads, it does not behave as a composite material. Specifically, during bolt embedment parallel to the fibers, matrix and fibers fail separately, the former tending to crush and the latter to buckle (Karagiannis et al., 2016). Hence, the typical numerical model assumption of homogeneous material of average material properties does not produce realistic results in terms of strength and stiffness. This is the case even when the simulation entails –computationally costly– complex material models and failure laws; e.g., pertinent studies for bolted wood connections usually produce stiffer connection behavior than the corresponding experimental tests (Patton-Mallory et al., 1997, Kharouf et al., 2003, Moses and Prion, 2004).

A remedy is to utilize in the numerical models a “bearing zone”, or “foundation zone” in the vicinity of the bolt (Hong, 2007, Karagiannis et al., 2016, Ramirez et al., 2012). This is a zone of (artificially) softer material, that aims to account for the apparent poorer material performance in that area. The

foundation zone is relatively simple in its implementation and computationally efficient. However, its size and material properties have mostly been empirical, determined by trial and error. The current strategy is to, first, select a foundation zone size, and, subsequently, to apply appropriate modification factors to the experimentally determined (via dowel-bearing tests) embedment material properties. The drawback in that case is that the modification factors and foundation zone size are case-specific, and thus cannot be implemented universally.

Because of the relative simplicity and computational efficiency of the foundation zone approach, this study adopts it to simulate embedment phenomena. The study proposes a rational methodology to specify the size and material properties of the foundation zone, without the need for embedment property modification. The goal is to accurately simulate numerically the average experimental behavior (in terms of strength and stiffness) of dowel-bearing tests and full-culm bamboo bolted connections.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Embedment properties (i.e., embedment strength and stiffness) depend on bolt diameter (e.g., Smith et al., 1988, Karagiannis et al., 2016, Trujillo & Malkowska, 2018). Hence, this study conducts a series of dowel-bearing tests on bamboo species Kao Jue (*Bambusa pervariabilis*), for three different bolt diameters: 6 mm, 8 mm, and 10 mm. As current bamboo standards (ISO 22156:2021, ISO 22157:2019) do not provide specifications on bamboo embedment property determination, the tests are conducted according to ASTM D5764. The specimens are pre-drilled, specimen height is approximately two times the culm diameter, and the bolts are not threaded. To prevent premature splitting (that occurs before embedment failure), this study utilizes confining steel rings (hose-clamps, fig. 1a).

Figure 1: Dowel-bearing experimental setup and results (embedment stress-normalized displacement curves).

Table 1: Dowel-bearing test summary (mean values \pm standard deviation)

bolt diameter d_b	no. of specimens	moisture content (%)	external diameter D (mm)	thickness t^* (mm)	embedment strength $\sigma_{emb,u}$ (MPa)	embedment stiffness E_{emb} (MPa)
6 mm	33	12.1 \pm 0.4	46.1 \pm 4.6	6.3 \pm 1.5	51.0 \pm 6.2	253 \pm 72.0
8 mm	33	10.3 \pm 0.2	44.1 \pm 3.3	5.4 \pm 0.8	47.8 \pm 6.5	309 \pm 74.6
10 mm	33	10.2 \pm 0.3	47.8 \pm 6.1	5.9 \pm 1.8	44.4 \pm 6.0	360 \pm 71.9

*mean value at the bolt contact locations

Table 1 provides specimen geometry and embedment properties for each bolt diameter. Embedment strength $\sigma_{emb,u}$ occurs as:

$$\sigma_{emb,u} = \frac{F_u}{2d_b t} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where t is the average thickness at the bolt contact points, d_b the bolt diameter, and F_u the experimental ‘‘yield’’ force, determined via the 5%-offset method. Embedment stiffness E_{emb} occurs from the slope of the experimental embedment stress-normalized (with bolt diameter) displacement curves (fig. 1) (e.g., Karagiannis et al., 2016, Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). Table 1 indicates that embedment strength decreases with bolt diameter, while embedment stiffness increases with bolt diameter. This is consistent with pertinent literature findings for timber (e.g., Smith et al., 1988, Karagiannis et al., 2016) and bamboo (e.g., Trujillo & Malkowska, 2018).

FOUNDATION MODELING

Adopting nominal material properties in numerical simulations that involve embedment phenomena (e.g., simulations of the dowel-bearing test or of bolted bamboo connections) fails to produce the experimentally observed behavior, in terms of strength and stiffness (e.g., Hong, 2007, Karagiannis et al., 2016, Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). To tackle this issue, this study adopts the foundation modeling approach. The approach consists in introducing in the numerical model a zone of softer material at the bolt vicinity (foundation zone). Currently, the material properties and size of the foundation zone have mostly been empirical, determined by trial-and-error (e.g., Hong, 2007, Ramirez et al., 2012, Karagiannis et al., 2016). This study adopts the nominal embedment properties (occurring from the dowel-bearing test, Table 1) as material properties of the foundation zone. Subsequently, the study determines the foundation zone depth rationally, on the premise that, at a stress level equal to the embedment strength, the foundation zone displacement of the equivalent model should be equal to the experimental ‘‘yield’’ displacement \bar{u}_{emb} :

$$\bar{u}_{emb} = \frac{\sigma_{emb,u} \cdot d_b}{E_{emb}} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where $\sigma_{emb,u}$ and E_{emb} are the embedment properties and d_b the bolt diameter.

To determine the foundation zone displacement, this section considers the stress and strain fields in the bolt vicinity. To that end, consider a uniform load p , acting on a finite length $2b$, on an orthotropic half-space (fig. 2a). Load p is an approximation of the load the bolt exerts on the bamboo culm during bolt embedment. The normal stresses σ_x and σ_y because of load p at a random point $K(x, y)$ of the orthotropic half-space (fig. 2a) are (Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos, 2021):

Figure 2: Analytical model used for the determination of the foundation zone depth

$$\sigma_x = \frac{p}{\pi\sqrt{\alpha}} \left[\frac{y(x-b)}{\alpha(x-b)^2 + y^2} - \frac{y(x+b)}{\alpha(x+b)^2 + y^2} - \frac{\tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha}(x-b)}{y}\right) - \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha}(x+b)}{y}\right)}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\sigma_y = \frac{p\sqrt{\alpha}}{\pi} \left[\frac{y(b-x)}{\alpha(x-b)^2 + y^2} + \frac{y(b+x)}{\alpha(x+b)^2 + y^2} + \frac{\tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha}(x+b)}{y}\right) - \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha}(x-b)}{y}\right)}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where α is a function of material properties in the x and y directions:

$$\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{\nu_{yx}}{\nu_{xy}}} = \sqrt{\frac{E_y}{E_x}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

In eq. 5, E_x and E_y are the Young's moduli in directions x and y respectively, and ν_{yx} , ν_{xy} the corresponding Poisson's ratios. Additionally, from elasticity theory, the strain values in the y direction occur as:

$$\varepsilon_y = \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y} - \frac{\nu_{xy}}{E_x} \sigma_x = \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y} - \frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_y} \sigma_x \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Subsequently, the foundation zone depth y_1 occurs solving the equation:

$$\bar{u}_{emb} = \int_0^{y_1} \varepsilon_y dy \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where \bar{u}_{emb} as in eq. 2, ε_y as in eq. 6, and the material properties that come into eq. 6 are the foundation zone material properties (nominal embedment properties, Table 1). Interestingly, assuming $\nu_{yx}=0.3$ (Ghavami & Marinho, 2005), and $\alpha = 3.2$ (Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos, 2020), eq. 7 gives $y_1 \approx 3.5d_b$ for all bolt diameters. Figure 2b shows that, at $y_1=3.5d_b$, the stress in direction y is approximately 30% of the imposed load p .

NUMERICAL MODELS

This section develops two sets of numerical models in the commercial finite element (FE) software Abaqus. First, the study simulates the conducted dowel-bearing tests (fig. 3), adopting the foundation modeling approach, to verify its accuracy in predicting the average experimental behavior in terms of strength and stiffness. Subsequently, the section adopts the foundation zone in FE models of bolted full-culm bamboo connections (fig. 4), investigating the effect of bolt diameter on connection performance.

Figure 3: Dowel-bearing test finite element model

Figure 4: Full-culm bamboo connection finite element model

Table 2: Numerical model material properties (stiffness and strength values in MPa)*

	nominal properties	foundation zone properties		
		6-mm bolt	8-mm bolt	10-mm bolt
radial modulus E_1	429	1000	1000	1000
circumferential modulus E_2	429	24	30	35
axial modulus E_3	4464	253	309	360
shear modulus G_{12}	176	10	12	14
shear modulus $G_{13}=G_{23}$	633	36	44	51
Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22
Poisson's ratio $\nu_{31}=\nu_{32}$	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
radial strength σ_{u1}	17.1	100.0	100.0	100.0
circumferential strength σ_{u2}	17.1	51.5	46.9	42.3
axial strength σ_{u3}	70.8	51	47.8	44.4
shear strength τ_{u12}	5.5	16.5	15.0	13.5
shear strength $\tau_{u13}=\tau_{u23}$	10.4	31.3	28.5	25.7

* direction notation: 1: radial direction, 2: circumferential direction, 3: axial direction

All models involve 3D solid, 8-node linear elements (24 degrees of freedom per element), and bamboo material properties as in Table 2. Nominal material properties are average experimental values reported in literature (Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos, 2021). Foundation zone material properties in the axial direction are experimental values determined via dowel-bearing tests (Table 1), while the rest of the properties occur analytically, according to the procedure described in Mouka & Dimitrakopoulos 2021, under the assumption of a transversely isotropic material. The high radial property values of the foundation zone (Table 2) aim to alleviate numerical instabilities inherent to the foundation modeling approach. Bolt material properties are $E = 180$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$ and yield strength $\sigma_y = 539$ MPa (average material strength). Mesh size is approximately 2.5 mm, with more refined mesh of approximately 1.5

mm at the foundation zone. In all models, load is applied as imposed displacement (figs. 3d, 4b). An important difference between the dowel-bearing test models and the connection models is that, in the former, the bolt does not deform, as opposed to the latter. Bamboo-bolt contact interface (figs. 3e, 4c) does not allow surface penetration in the normal direction, and includes friction in the tangential direction, with friction coefficient $\mu=0.3$. The analyses employ the Static, General solver (which is based on the Newton-Raphson method), and take into account non-linear geometric effects. To reduce computational cost, all models employ symmetry, simulating one-quarter of the test geometry in the case of the dowel-bearing tests, and half of the geometry in the case of the full-culm bamboo connections. Figures 3b and 4b illustrate the assigned boundary conditions, after applying symmetry.

Figure 5 compares the experimental dowel-bearing test results with the corresponding FE model results. It shows that the foundation modeling approach accurately predicts the average experimental behavior (in terms of strength and stiffness). Figure 6a compares the full-culm bamboo connection FE model results with corresponding experimental results (Paraskeva et al, 2019). The figure showcases the applicability of the proposed foundation modeling approach also in the case of full-culm bamboo connections. Figure 6b illustrates numerical model results on the effect of bolt diameter on connection behavior. As expected, connection stiffness increases with increasing bolt diameter. The stiffness increase is more prominent between 6 mm and 8 mm bolts, than between 8 mm and 10 mm bolts. This is also expected, as, apart from the foundation zone stiffness (which increases almost linearly with bolt diameter, Table 1), connection stiffness also depends on bolt deformations (bolt bending stiffness). Connection yield load also increases with increasing bolt diameter, indicating that bolt yield load is more critical than embedment strength (embedment strength decreases with bolt diameter, Table 1) in the determination of connection yield load.

Figure 5: Comparison between experimental and numerical (in the model: $D = 45$ mm, $t = 6$ mm) embedment stress-normalized displacement curves (dowel-bearing test).

Figure 6: Numerical results for the full-culm bamboo connections (model geometry: $D = 45$ mm, $t = 5$ mm)

CONCLUSIONS

This study conducts dowel-bearing tests on bamboo culms, to determine bamboo embedment properties for three different bolt diameters. Subsequently, it proposes a methodology for the numerical simulation of embedment phenomena. Basis for the proposed methodology is the well-known foundation modeling approach. The study proposes a rational procedure for the determination of foundation zone size and material properties, without the need for arbitrary property modification factors. Foundation zone size occurs from analytical expressions of the stress field in the bolt vicinity, while foundation zone material properties are the experimentally determined embedment properties. The occurring foundation zone depth is 3.5 bolt diameters, and the foundation zone width is one bolt diameter. Comparison of experimental results with finite element model results verify the applicability of the proposed methodology for the prediction of strength and stiffness of dowel-bearing tests and full-culm bamboo connections. Thus, the proposed methodology can facilitate the design and optimization of full-culm bamboo connections, minimizing the amount tests needed.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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